

GENDER-RESPONSIVE TEACHING METHODS OF TOURISM MANAGEMENT DEPARTMENT FACULTY AT CAPIZ STATE UNIVERSITY SIGMA SATELLITE COLLEGE

Jhannel J. Abalajon¹, Ginalyn J. Obien¹, Roselyn P. Cabantud¹, Ramy Lloyd L. Lotilla²,
Kirsty G. Tanque³, Augustin C. Borbon³, Roselyn D. Yangao³, Marie Anne J. Vallejo³,
Jocelyn A. Magallanes², Yhanie A. Lantoria³

¹*Hospitality Management Department, Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College,
Philippines*

²*Technical teacher Education, Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College, Philippines*

³*Tourism Management Department, Capiz State University, Roxas City, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14026446>

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of gender-responsive teaching methods in the Tourism Management Department at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College, aiming to evaluate the effectiveness of current practices in fostering gender inclusivity. Employing a descriptive and quantitative research design, structured surveys were distributed to 217 tourism management students, yielding 201 responses. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential tests to assess students' perceptions of gender-responsive teaching methods. Key findings indicate a neutral overall perception of these methods, highlighting the need for enhanced faculty training to improve the integration of inclusivity in classroom settings. Additionally, both classroom setups and learning materials received neutral ratings, suggesting significant room for improvement in creating a more inclusive educational environment. Notably, the analysis revealed significant differences in perceptions based on students' gender and year level, emphasizing the necessity of considering socio-demographic factors when evaluating and implementing gender-responsive teaching strategies. These results advocate for tailored interventions and curriculum adjustments to promote gender equality and enhance teaching effectiveness, aligning with existing educational recommendations. To address these gaps, it is recommended that Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College invest in comprehensive teacher training programs to better equip educators with

the skills needed to foster inclusive practices and effectively address gender-related issues within their classrooms.

Keywords: *Inclusive Classroom Comfort, Fair and Equal Treatment, Evolving Gender-Responsive Practices, Inclusive Teaching Materials, Gender-neutral Language, Gender Sensitivity Teacher training*

INTRODUCTION

Gender inequality in education remains a significant challenge, particularly in developing countries like the Philippines, despite ongoing efforts to promote gender equality. Gender responsive pedagogy for improving learning outcomes: Implications for teacher education in Africa (2018) by Sarah Ayeri Ogallo. The proposed research at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College (CAPSU) seeks to address this issue by implementing gender-responsive teaching methods within the Tourism Management Department Faculty. This initiative is driven by the findings of the United Nations Girls' Education Initiative (UNGEI, 2016)), which emphasize the importance of creating a safe and inclusive learning environment that caters to the needs and interests of all students, especially girls (UNGEI, 2016). The UNGEI framework provides practical strategies for teachers to combat gender biases and foster a supportive learning environment. Statistical data reveal persistent gender disparities in the Philippines' education system. For instance, in 2020, the primary completion rate for girls was 83.9%, compared to 88.8% for boys, and literacy rates for women were 63%, versus 80% for men (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2020). These figures highlight the need for targeted interventions to close gender gaps in education. The UNESCO report on gender-responsive teaching further supports this by offering recommendations for integrating gender-sensitive practices into teacher education programs, such as addressing gender stereotypes and promoting equal participation in classrooms (UNESCO, 2020).

The research aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5): Gender Equality, as defined by UNICEF. SDG 5 aims to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls, with a focus on eliminating gender disparities in education and ensuring equal access to quality education (UNICEF, 2024). By implementing gender-responsive teaching methods, this research directly contributes to this goal by fostering an equitable learning environment that supports both male and female students and addresses systemic gender biases. Utilizing a quantitative approach, the study will measure the effectiveness of the implemented teaching methods through statistical analysis. Data will be collected from students to assess their experiences and perceptions of gender responsiveness in the classroom, providing a clear understanding of the impact of these methods on gender equality within the educational environment.

The expected outputs of this research include a comprehensive report on the level of gender-responsive teaching methods, a set of recommendations for enhancing these practices, and an evaluation report. These outputs will provide valuable insights for

policymakers and educators, facilitating the creation of more inclusive educational practices. By aligning with guidelines from the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) and the Education and Development Forum, the research will offer evidence-based recommendations to enhance gender sensitivity in teaching and learning environments (UNFPA, 2012; Education and Development Forum, 2018). The research justifies resource expenditure through its potential to significantly improve gender equality in education. By addressing gender disparities, the study will not only benefit CAPSU Sigma Satellite College but also serve as a model for other institutions. Ultimately, this initiative supports sustainable development goals by promoting equal educational opportunities, which are crucial for social and economic advancement in the country, aligning with SDG 5 and the broader objectives of gender equality and empowerment (UNICEF, n.d.).

The primary objective of the study is to assess the gender-responsive teaching methods employed by the Tourism Management Department Faculty at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College. Specifically, the research seeks to determine the socio-demographic profile of the tourism management students in terms of age, gender, and year level. It also aims to evaluate the level gender-responsive teaching methods by examining key aspects such as teaching skills, classroom setup, learning materials, and classroom dynamics and interaction. Furthermore, the research will investigate whether there are significant differences in the level of gender-responsive teaching methods when categorized according to the students' socio-demographic profiles. Ultimately, the findings of this study will contribute to the development of more inclusive and effective educational practices, supporting efforts to promote gender equality within the academic community.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the gender-responsive teaching methods employed by the Tourism Management Department Faculty at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of, age, gender, and year level?
2. What is the level of gender-responsive teaching methods employed by Tourism Management Department Faculty of Capiz State University in terms of, key teaching skills, classroom set up, learning and teaching materials and, classroom dynamics and interaction?
3. What is the experience of students towards the gender-responsiveness of Tourism Management Department Faculty at Capiz State University?
4. Is there a significant difference on the level of gender-responsive Teaching Methods of Tourism Management Department Faculty of CAPSU Sigma in terms of, key teaching skills, classroom set up, learning and teaching materials and, classroom dynamics and interaction between CAPSU Sigma satellite college?

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this study employed a descriptive research design taking on mix method (quantitative and qualitative data analysis) to assess gender-responsive teaching methods within the Tourism Management Department at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College. This design was selected to systematically analyze current teaching practices and their effects on students. Structured surveys were used to collect and analyze numerical data, facilitating a comprehensive quantitative assessment of the findings.

Cochran's formula was applied to determine an appropriate sample size, ensuring representation across the student population. A total of 217 tourism management students were randomly selected, minimizing selection bias. The study achieved a high survey retrieval rate of 93%, with 201 responses collected, enhancing the reliability of the results.

Data analysis utilized descriptive statistics, such as means, frequencies, and percentages, to summarize the findings. Inferential statistics, including t-tests and ANOVA, were employed to identify significant differences in the application of gender-responsive teaching methods based on students' socio-demographic profiles. Additionally, Pearson correlation analysis assessed the strength and direction of relationships between these teaching methods and various socio-demographic factors.

This methodological framework provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of gender-responsive teaching practices and informs future educational strategies aimed at promoting gender equality within the institution. Ethical considerations, including securing informed consent and ensuring participant anonymity, were rigorously observed throughout the research process. Data collection utilized both Google Forms and physical surveys, with a structured questionnaire covering demographic profiles and motivational factors. Content validity was established through reviews by academic experts, refining the questionnaire for clarity and relevance. Quantitative data analysis was conducted using SPSS software, while qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis based on Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach. An approved letter from the Office of the President confirmed the study's legitimacy, ensuring adherence to institutional protocols. While the findings provide a comprehensive understanding of student motivation, they may be limited to the specific population of tourism management students at this institution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic Profile of the Tourism Management College Students

Table 1 reveals the socio-demographic profile of Tourism Management college students. Specifically, it shows that a dominant majority (91%) of students are below 18 years old, indicating a youthful population within the program. In terms of gender, females

constitute a significant portion of the population, with 77% compared to 23% males. This gender distribution suggests a female-majority enrollment in the program. Furthermore, the data indicates that 1st-year students make up 38% of the population, followed by 3rd-year students at 33%, and 4th-year students at 27%, with only 1% in the 2nd year. The relatively balanced distribution across year levels, except for the low representation in the 2nd year, implies that the program is primarily attracting younger students, particularly females. This trend may influence the design of future curricula and support services to cater more effectively to the needs of this demographic. The findings align with the broader understanding of gender disparities in education, where female students often dominate in specific academic programs, as noted in studies by Ogalo (2018) and others. These insights suggest that targeted interventions to further support female students' academic and professional development are essential.

Table 1. Socio-demographic Profile of the Tourism Management College Students

Socio-demographic Profile	N	Percentage
Age		
Below 18 years old	183	91%
18-22	15	7.5%
23-27	2	1%
28-32	1	0.5%
Gender		
Male	46	23%
Female	155	77%
Year level		
1st year	77	38%
2nd Year	1	1%
3rd Year	67	33%
4th Year	56	27%

Gender-responsive Teaching Methods of Tourism Management Department Faculty

Table 2 focuses on key teaching skills related to gender-responsive practices in the classroom. Across all statements, the mean score consistently averages at 2.51, with a standard deviation of 1.26, which can be interpreted as neutral. This neutrality suggests that students perceive the current teaching practices as neither strongly inclusive nor exclusive of gender considerations. For instance, the use of inclusive language and encouragement of diverse participation received neutral ratings, indicating that while some efforts may be in place, they may not be consistently recognized or impactful. This findings of Nillesen and van de Kamp (2019), who highlighted that despite the presence of gender-responsive methods, their effectiveness often depends on the extent of their integration into everyday teaching practices. The implication of these findings suggests that there is room for improvement in training faculty to be more aware and proactive in

gender-responsive teaching methods. By enhancing these practices, educators can create a more inclusive environment that supports diverse student engagement and learning outcomes, as recommended by UNESCO (2012).

Gender-responsive teaching methods include a variety of strategies and practices designed to address gender-related issues in the classroom. These approaches encompass using gender-neutral language, incorporating gender-sensitive materials and examples, fostering opportunities for both girls and boys to learn and interact together, and promoting critical thinking about gender stereotypes and biases. Research has demonstrated the effectiveness of these methods in advancing gender equality in education. For instance, a study conducted in Nigeria revealed that implementing gender-responsive teaching methods resulted in improved academic performance and increased confidence among female students. Similarly, research in Kenya found that gender-responsive pedagogy enhanced participation and engagement among girls in science and mathematics subjects (Nillesen & van de Kamp, 2019). In their study on rural schools in Nepal, explore the challenges and opportunities associated with implementing gender-responsive teaching methods, offering valuable insights into their potential impact on student learning outcomes.

Table 2. Key Teaching Skills

Key Teaching Skills				
No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Professors use inclusive language, like saying 'they' instead of 'he or she,' making everyone feel included.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
2	Teachers actively call on different students, not just the usual volunteers, ensuring everyone has a chance to participate.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
3	Faculty encourage respectful debate and challenge gender stereotypes in class discussions, expanding our perspectives.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
4	Professors create safe spaces for open discussions about gender and identity, fostering understanding and empathy.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
5	Some teachers rely heavily on lectures and do not utilize interactive methods that encourage diverse participation.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
6	I have not noticed any specific efforts to address unconscious bias in the way professors call on students."	2.51	1.26	Neutral

7	While respectful of individual opinions, discussions on gender sometimes lack deeper analysis of societal inequalities.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
8	Creating a safe space for discussion depends heavily on individual faculty, not always university-wide practice.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
9	Professors sometimes use gendered jokes or language that make me feel uncomfortable and excluded.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
10	I witness students making sexist comments in class, and the teacher rarely intervenes or addresses them.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
11	The classroom environment does not feel inclusive to diverse gender identities or expressions, hindering open participation.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
12	Faculty lack training or awareness on using inclusive language and facilitating discussions sensitive to gender issues.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
Grand Mean		2.51	1.26	Neutral

Table 3 evaluates the classroom setup concerning gender inclusivity. Similar to the previous table, all statements received a neutral mean score of 2.51 with a standard deviation of 1.26. This neutrality reflects students' perceptions that the classroom environment neither significantly supports nor hinders gender inclusivity. For example, while the presence of rotating group tables and accessible bathrooms promotes inclusivity, traditional seating arrangements and limited gender-sensitive resources seem to counterbalance these efforts. The neutral feedback implies that while some inclusive practices are present, they may not be fully integrated or effective in creating a gender-responsive classroom environment. As Ndlovu and Mkhize (2019) point out, the physical setup of a classroom plays a crucial role in either fostering or hindering gender-inclusive learning experiences. Therefore, there is a need for more deliberate efforts in designing and managing classroom spaces to ensure they are truly inclusive and conducive to all students' learning. In the Philippines, various initiatives have been established to promote gender-responsive teaching methods in the classroom. These initiatives encompass the development of gender-responsive teaching guides, training programs for educators, and the integration of gender-responsive strategies into the K-12 curriculum. Lessons learned from these efforts underscore the significance of addressing gender stereotypes and biases, promoting positive role models for women and girls, and creating inclusive learning environments that celebrate diversity. Additionally, these initiatives emphasize the necessity for ongoing teacher training and support, as well as the importance of engaging parents, communities, and other stakeholders to foster gender equality in education. It further highlights the current state

of gender-responsive pedagogy in South Africa, offering critical reflections and recommendations to address challenges and gaps in implementing these methods within the education system.

Table 3. Classroom Set-up

Classroom Set-up				
No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	The classroom has rotating group tables, encouraging collaboration and interaction across genders.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
2	Posters celebrating diverse individuals and achievements make me feel welcome and seen in the space.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
3	There are accessible bathrooms for everyone, regardless of gender identity, promoting inclusivity.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
4	Open and flexible seating arrangements create a dynamic environment where everyone feels comfortable participating.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
5	The desks are arranged in traditional rows, limiting collaboration and interaction between students.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
6	There are limited resources or displays specifically focused on gender equality or inclusivity.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
7	Gendered signage for bathrooms (e.g., 'boys' and 'girls') feels outdated and potentially exclusionary.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
8	The classroom feels overcrowded, making it difficult for students to move around and interact freely.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
9	Seating charts reinforce traditional gender roles, with boys often placed in the back and girls in the front.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
10	"Gender-stereotypical imagery or decorations (e.g., pink for girls, blue for boys) are present in the classroom.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
11	Limited accessibility features (e.g., ramps, wider doorways) create barriers for students with diverse needs.	2.51	1.26	Neutral

12	The classroom environment feels rigid and traditional, hindering active participation and diverse expression.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
Grand Mean		2.51	1.26	Neutral

Table 4 assesses the inclusivity of learning and teaching materials. Consistently, the mean score of 2.51 and a standard deviation of 1.26 across all statements suggest a neutral perception among students regarding the gender responsiveness of these materials. This neutrality indicates that while some materials may include diverse perspectives and challenge stereotypes, others may still reinforce traditional gender roles and lack inclusivity. This finding is supported by the research of Ngo and Rosen (2019), who argue that while educational materials have made strides towards inclusivity, there remains a significant gap in fully addressing and integrating gender-sensitive content. The implication of these findings is that the curriculum could benefit from a more comprehensive review and integration of diverse, inclusive content. Ensuring that learning materials reflect a broad range of gender experiences and promote critical thinking on gender-related issues could significantly enhance students' educational experiences and contribute to a more equitable learning environment, as supported by the Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5) framework (UNICEF, n.d.). Despite the potential benefits of gender-responsive teaching methods, several barriers and challenges hinder their implementation in the classroom. These include a lack of awareness and understanding of gender-related issues among educators, cultural and societal norms that reinforce gender stereotypes and biases, and insufficient resources and support for gender-responsive teaching. Additionally, challenges arise from the need for sustained teacher training and support, along with potential resistance from students and parents who may be accustomed to traditional gender roles and expectations. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach, including the need to confront underlying cultural and societal norms, provide adequate resources and support for educators, and actively engage parents and communities to promote gender equality in education. According to Ngo and Rosen (2019), their report highlights various gender-responsive teaching methods, emphasizing their theoretical foundations, effectiveness, and best practices, and offers examples from around the world.

Table 4. Learning and Teaching Materials

Learning and Teaching Materials				
No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Textbooks and articles showcase diverse voices and perspectives across genders, broadening my understanding.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
2	Case studies feature individuals and groups challenging gender stereotypes, sparking critical thinking.	2.51	1.26	Neutral

3	Assignments encourage collaboration and consider different points of view on gender-related issues.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
4	Teachers provide supplementary materials (e.g., videos, articles) representing diverse gender identities.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
5	Most readings focus on historical figures or events, lacking representation of contemporary gender issues.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
6	Course materials use predominantly male pronouns and examples, even when referring to general concepts."	2.51	1.26	Neutral
7	Assignments rarely address or challenge traditional gender roles and stereotypes.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
8	Limited access to diverse materials limits exposure to various perspectives on gender.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
9	Some textbooks contain outdated or offensive language and portrayals of gender roles.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
10	Case studies perpetuate harmful stereotypes and lack analysis of systemic gender inequalities.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
11	Assignments reinforce traditional gender norms and fail to acknowledge diverse experiences.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
12	There is a lack of awareness or effort to integrate inclusive and representative materials in the curriculum.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
Grand Mean		2.51	1.26	Neutral

Table 5 explores the dynamics of classroom interaction with respect to gender. The overall mean of 2.66, with a standard deviation of 0.97, leans slightly towards neutral, but with higher scores in statements concerning microaggressions and traditional gender roles, which received mean scores of 3.04 and 3.11, respectively. This suggests that while general classroom interactions are perceived as neutral, there are concerns about microaggressions and the reinforcement of traditional gender roles, which negatively impact the inclusivity of the learning environment. The findings imply that despite some efforts towards inclusive interaction, there are underlying issues related to gender dynamics that need to be addressed. This is in line with studies from Nigeria and

Kenya, which demonstrate that while gender-responsive teaching can improve classroom dynamics, it requires consistent effort and awareness from educators to be truly effective (Ogalo, 2018). Consequently, more focused interventions are necessary to create a classroom culture that actively supports diverse participation and challenges harmful stereotypes. These interventions could contribute to fostering a more inclusive educational environment, ultimately supporting the goals of gender equality in education as outlined by the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA, 2012). Despite the potential benefits of gender-responsive teaching methods, several barriers and challenges impede their effective implementation in the classroom. These barriers include a lack of awareness and understanding of gender-related issues among educators, cultural and societal norms that perpetuate gender stereotypes and biases, and insufficient resources and support for gender-responsive teaching. Additionally, the need for ongoing teacher training and support is critical, as is the potential resistance from students and parents who may adhere to traditional gender roles and expectations. To address these challenges, a multi-faceted approach is necessary, focusing on changing underlying cultural and societal norms, providing adequate resources and support for educators, and engaging parents and communities to promote gender equality in education. Their report offers an overview of gender-responsive teaching methods, highlighting their theoretical foundations, effectiveness, and best practices, along with examples from various educational contexts worldwide.

Table 5. Classroom Dynamics and Interaction

Classroom Dynamics and Interaction				
No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Professors actively encourage and respect participation from all students, regardless of gender.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
2	Class discussions prioritize respectful debate and challenge harmful stereotypes, fostering open dialogue.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
3	Group work promotes collaboration and understanding amongst students from diverse backgrounds.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
4	The professor creates a safe space for students to share their perspectives and experiences related to gender.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
5	Some students hesitate to participate due to fear of judgment, hindering diverse voices in discussions.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
6	Professors rarely intervene when sexist comments or jokes are made, creating an uncomfortable environment.	2.51	1.26	Neutral

7	Teacher-centered lectures limit opportunities for student interaction and expression of various viewpoints.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
8	"Classroom discussions primarily focus on academic content, rarely addressing real-world gender issues."	2.51	1.26	Neutral
9	Certain students dominate discussions, making it difficult for others, especially minorities, to contribute.	2.51	1.26	Neutral
10	Microaggressions based on gender identity or expression go unnoticed and unaddressed, creating a hostile environment.	3.04	1.13	High
11	The classroom culture reinforces traditional gender roles, discouraging open dialogues and diverse participation.	3.11	1.22	High
12	Students with differing opinions on gender-related topics fear expressing themselves openly due to potential backlash.	3.21	1.18	High
Grand Mean		2.66	0.97	Neutral

Significant Difference on the Level of Gender-responsive Teaching Methods Tourism Management Department Faculty of CAPSU Sigma when respondents are grouped according to its socio-demographic profile

Table 6 highlights the differences in perceptions of gender-responsive teaching methods among the Tourism Management Department faculty at CAPSU Sigma when respondents are grouped by their socio-demographic profiles. Age has a P-value of 0.91, indicating no significant difference in perceptions based on age. This finding suggests that age does not significantly affect how gender-responsive teaching methods are perceived. In contrast, gender, and year level show significant differences, with P-values of less than 0.001. This significant result for gender is consistent with research showing that gender can influence perceptions and effectiveness of teaching methods (Ogalo, 2018; Nillesen & van de Kamp, 2019). Similarly, the significant difference related to year level could reflect variations in experience or exposure to gender-responsive practices over time, as discussed in the context of educational environments (Ndlovu & Mkhize, 2019). These findings underscore the importance of considering socio-demographic factors when evaluating and implementing gender-responsive teaching methods.

Table 6. Significant Difference on the Level of Gender-responsive Teaching Methods Tourism Management Department Faculty of CAPSU Sigma when respondents are grouped according to its socio-demographic profile

Socio-demographic Profiles	f	P-value	Verbal Interpretation
Age	0.01	0.91	Not Significant
Gender	5.86	<.001	Significant
Year	22459.67	<.001	Significant

Experiences of Students towards the Gender-Responsiveness of Teachers at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College

Inclusive Classroom Comfort

At Capiz State University (CapSU), students report feeling comfortable expressing their opinions on gender-related topics. This sense of comfort is crucial for fostering open discussions in the classroom. Many participants noted that teachers actively encourage participation from all genders, creating an inclusive atmosphere where students can share their experiences without fear of judgment. This supportive environment allows students to feel respected and valued, which enhances their engagement and willingness to contribute to discussions. One participant highlighted this sentiment by stating, "I feel comfortable sharing my opinions because I speak from my experiences." Such feedback underscores the positive dynamics in the classroom, where inclusive practices are not just encouraged but actively promoted by educators. Several policy frameworks and guidelines promote gender equality in education, including Sustainable Development Goal 4 on quality education, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), and the UNESCO Gender Equality in Education Framework (GEF). These frameworks emphasize the necessity of creating a gender-responsive and inclusive learning environment that effectively addresses gender-related issues and promotes equal opportunities for all students (Dryden-Peterson & Amatya, 2019). They also underscore the role of gender-responsive teaching methods in advancing gender equality in education, particularly in combating gender stereotypes, biases, and discrimination within the classroom. According to Dryden-Peterson and Amatya (2019), their guide offers practical strategies and tools for implementing gender-responsive teaching methods across diverse settings, including refugee and humanitarian contexts. Additionally, the guide provides recommendations for teacher development programs to effectively integrate gender-responsive pedagogy into their curricula.

Fair and Equal Treatment

The theme of fair and equal treatment emerges as a significant aspect of students' experiences at CapSU. Most students reported that they are treated equally by both teachers and classmates, contributing to a generally inclusive environment. Many participants expressed that they had not witnessed or experienced any gender-based discrimination, which suggests that the university's efforts to create an equitable space are effective. One student remarked, "Everyone is treated equally in class. There is no discrimination," reflecting a shared understanding among students that inclusivity is prioritized. This perception of equality is essential for fostering a sense of belonging

among students, regardless of their gender identity. However, there are indications that continuous efforts are needed to sustain this environment, particularly in maintaining consistent practices across all classrooms.

Evolving Gender-Responsive Practices

While many teachers at CapSU are making strides in utilizing inclusive language and addressing gender issues, there is a recognized need for further improvement in training and resources. Some students noted that, although inclusive practices are present, not all educators fully embrace them, which can lead to inconsistencies in the classroom experience. One participant suggested, "The materials used for teaching should be reviewed to eliminate stereotypes or biases," indicating that there is still work to be done. This feedback highlights the importance of ongoing professional development for teachers, particularly regarding gender sensitivity and responsiveness. By enhancing training programs, CapSU can ensure that all educators are equipped to foster an inclusive environment that respects and values diverse gender identities. Continuous evaluation and refinement of teaching practices will be vital in advancing the university's commitment to gender inclusivity.

Overall, students at CapSU feel comfortable expressing their opinions about gender, thanks to the inclusive environment fostered by their teachers. Most educators actively encourage participation and challenge harmful stereotypes, contributing to a supportive learning atmosphere. While many students report no experiences of sexism or bias, there is a recognized need for ongoing discussions about gender issues to deepen awareness and understanding. Efforts to integrate diverse perspectives into the curriculum are underway, but there remains room for improvement in representing different gender views.

Experiences of Students towards the Gender-Responsiveness of Teachers at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College	Codes	Representative Excerpts from Qualitative Interviews
1. Inclusive Classroom Comfort (25)	Comfortable sharing opinions Teachers encourage participation Inclusive language practices LGBTQIA+ support Respect for all genders No discrimination experienced	"I feel comfortable sharing my opinions in class." "Teachers always encourage everyone to participate." "The use of inclusive language makes a big difference."

<p>2. Fair and Equal Treatment (22)</p>	<p>Everyone treated equally (6 mentions) No gender bias witnessed (5 mentions) Teachers provide fair opportunities (4 mentions) Fair discipline (4 mentions) Equality in teaching materials (3 mentions) Inclusive teaching materials</p>	<p>"I've never witnessed any form of gender bias in our classes." "Teachers ensure everyone gets equal opportunities." "The materials used in class are fair for all genders."</p>
<p>3. Evolving Gender-Responsive Practices (19)</p>	<p>Gender-neutral language Proactive gender discussions Need for more teacher training Supportive classroom environment</p>	<p>"The materials we use are inclusive of all genders." "I believe we need more discussions about gender issues." "There is a supportive environment for everyone in class."</p>

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. The program mainly attracts younger females, suggesting that curriculum and support services should be tailored to meet the needs of this demographic.
2. The neutral perception of gender-responsive teaching methods indicate a need for improved faculty training to better integrate inclusivity in the classroom.
3. Students at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College largely feel comfortable expressing their opinions and perceive fair treatment regarding gender, although ongoing improvements in teacher training and curriculum inclusivity are necessary to further enhance the gender-responsive environment.
4. Significant differences in perceptions based on gender and year level highlight the importance of considering socio-demographic factors in evaluating and implementing gender-responsive teaching methods.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations have been made:

1. It is recommended that the curriculum and support services for the Tourism Management program be specifically designed to cater to the needs and preferences of the predominantly younger female student population.

2. It is recommended that faculty receive enhanced training on gender-responsive teaching methods to better integrate inclusivity and address the current neutral perceptions among students.
3. It is recommended that Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College enhance teacher training programs to better equip educators with the skills to promote inclusive practices and address gender-related issues effectively.
4. It is recommended to consider socio-demographic factors, such as gender and year level, when evaluating and implementing gender-responsive teaching methods to better address diverse perceptions and needs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors of the study titled "Gender-Responsive Teaching Methods of Tourism Management Department Faculty at Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College" are committed to upholding ethical research practices throughout the study. Prior to data collection, an approved letter from the Office of the President was obtained, confirming the research's legitimacy and compliance with institutional protocols. Informed consent was secured from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of their rights and the study's nature. Participants were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any repercussions. Anonymity was maintained to protect the identities of all respondents, and their well-being was prioritized throughout the research process. The authors declare that no conflicts of interest exist in relation to this study, and they have rigorously avoided plagiarism in all aspects of their work. Furthermore, they ensured that the interpretation of findings was free from bias, using the results solely for research purposes. This stringent adherence to ethical standards reinforces the validity and reliability of the study's conclusions.

Acknowledgements

The researchers would like to extend their deepest gratitude to everyone who has supported and contributed to the completion of this research. To their family and friends, your unwavering encouragement and understanding have been invaluable throughout this journey. A heartfelt thank you goes to the students who participated in the survey; your insights and cooperation were crucial to the success of this study. The researchers are profoundly grateful to Dr. Lotilla for the expert statistical guidance that significantly enhanced the quality of their analysis. They also wish to acknowledge the faculty and staff at Capiz State University for their unwavering support and dedication, which played a vital role in bringing this research to fruition. Additionally, the researchers extend their appreciation to the university's top-level management for fostering an environment that encourages academic excellence. Most importantly, they give thanks to their dear Lord for guiding them through every challenge and blessing this endeavor with success. Your collective support and contributions have made this research possible, and for that, they are truly thankful.

REFERENCES

- Braun, Virginia & Clarke, Victoria. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3, 77-101. doi: 10.1191/1478088706qp0630a.
- Dryden-Peterson, S., & Amatya, K. (2019). *Gender-Responsive Teaching and Teacher Development: A Primer for Educators and Humanitarians*. Technical report. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Graduate School of Education. Retrieved from <https://www.hks.harvard.edu/sites/default/files/centers/cid/files/publications/faculty-working-papers/dryden-peterson-and-amatya-gender-responsive-teaching-and-teacher-development-july-2019.pdf>
- Ndlovu, Z., & Mkhize, N. (2019). Gender-responsive pedagogy in South Africa: Critical reflections and recommendations for the future. *Agenda*, 33(2), 52-63. doi: 10.1080/10130950.2019.1611176
- Ngo, V. W., & Rosen, L. H. (2019). *Gender-Responsive Teaching and Learning: A Review of Literature and Promising Practices*. Technical report. New York: Women's Refugee Commission. Retrieved from <https://www.womensrefugeecommission.org/resources/gender-responsive-teaching-and-learning-a-review-of-literature-and-promising-practices/>
- Nillesen, E. M., & van de Kamp, J. (2019). Gender-responsive education and teaching practices in rural schools in Nepal. *Gender and Education*, 31(5), 597-614. doi: 10.1080/09540253.2018.1559058
- Ogalo, S. A. (2018). Gender responsive pedagogy for improving learning outcomes: Implications for teacher education in Africa. *Gender and Education*, 30(4), 431-446. doi: 10.1080/09540253.2017.1362936
- The Education and Development Forum. (2018). *The role of gender-responsive teaching in reducing gender inequalities in education: Evidence from Ghana*. <https://www.ukfiet.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/The-role-of-gender-responsive-teaching-in-reducing-gender-inequalities-in-education-evidence-from-Ghana.pdf>
- UNICEF. (2024). *UNICEF and the Sustainable Development Goals*. UNICEF. <https://www.unicef.org/sdgs>
- United Nations Development Programme. (2008). *Gender-sensitive pedagogy: Teacher's manual*. <https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/womens-empowerment/gender-sensitive-pedagogy-teachers-manual.html>
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2012). *Gender-responsive teaching and learning in teacher education*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000219269>
- United Nations Girls' Education Initiative. (2016). *Gender-responsive pedagogy: A framework for teaching girls*. <https://www.ungei.org/infobycountry/gender-responsive-pedagogy-framework-teaching-girls>
- United Nations Population Fund. (2012). *Gender-sensitive pedagogy in action: Teacher's manual*. <https://www.unfpa.org/resources/gender-sensitive-pedagogy-action-teachers-manual>

